

Study to Find Relationship between Link to Organization and Job Embeddedness: A Moderation Effect

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Abstract

This study examines job embeddedness within Indian higher education through three dimensions: links, fit, and sacrifice. Links encompass relationships with colleagues and community, creating a sense of belonging vital to faculty satisfaction. Fit represents the alignment between personal values and institutional goals, while sacrifice refers to the perceived costs of leaving, such as tenure or research continuity. The study also explores gender differences, noting that female faculty often emphasize flexible work options and support systems, which influence their embeddedness uniquely. Using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM), the findings suggest that fostering fit, professional networks, and institutional flexibility are essential to reducing turnover. This research supports holistic retention strategies that recognize diverse needs, facilitating an academic environment where faculty feel genuinely embedded.

Keywords: Job Embeddedness, Academicians, Moderation, link to organization, Gender

Introduction

Job embeddedness (JE), first introduced by Mitchell *et al.*, (2001), brings a fresh perspective to understanding why people stay in their jobs. Rather than focusing solely on whether employees feel satisfied or dissatisfied with their work, job embeddedness considers a bigger picture. It captures the broader life context that influences employees' decisions, emphasizing both work-related and personal factors. This holistic approach has gained a lot of attention in recent years, as it provides a deeper understanding of what keeps employees rooted in their roles (Lee *et al.*, 2004).

In the past two decades, organizations have faced increasing difficulty in holding onto talent. With the work environment becoming more complex—driven by the rise of remote work, a more mobile workforce, and changing values—retaining employees has become more challenging. Today, work-life balance and personal fulfilment are just as important to employees as traditional incentives like salary (Nguyen *et al.*, 2020). In this shifting landscape, job embeddedness has proven to be a valuable tool for companies to understand and address turnover risks. Unlike earlier models that focused on why employees might leave (like dissatisfaction or management conflicts), job embeddedness examines the reasons employees stay. These factors, which include social relationships, personal investments, and the perceived sacrifices of leaving, can greatly increase retention—even when employees may not be entirely happy with their current job (Zhang *et al.*, 2012).

Components of JE

Job embeddedness is often broken down into three key elements: links, fit, and sacrifice. Each of these dimensions helps explain why people feel tied to their jobs and communities, and why they are less likely to leave.

Links: These are the formal and informal connections that employees build within their organizations and communities. These links can include relationships with coworkers, family ties, or participation in community activities. All these connections contribute to a sense of belonging, making it harder for the employee to leave (Ng and Feldman, 2010).

Fit: This refers to how well employees feel their personal values, goals, and abilities match the demands of their job and organization. When employees feel a strong fit, they tend to experience greater job satisfaction and a stronger commitment to their organization, which

reduces their likelihood of leaving (Jiang *et al.*, 2012). This sense of fit isn't just about work—it extends to how well their personal lives align with their broader environment, whether that's the culture of the organization or the appeal of the location they live in.

Sacrifice: This dimension is about what employees believe they would lose if they left their job. These sacrifices might include financial losses (like salary or benefits) or personal and social costs (such as friendships or professional networks). Research shows that the more significant these perceived sacrifices, the more likely employees are to stay (Holtom *et al.*, 2008). Sacrifice also includes emotional investments—employees often stay because they have poured so much of themselves into their work and relationships (Allen, 2006).

Theoretical Foundations

Job embeddedness emerged as a response to traditional models of turnover that centered on dissatisfaction or organizational commitment as the main reasons for employees leaving (Mobley, 1977; Meyer and Allen, 1991). While these models offered valuable insights, they often focused too narrowly on negative experiences at work. Job embeddedness, on the other hand, offers a more comprehensive view, considering factors like social ties, community involvement, and personal investments that influence the decision of the employee to stay in the company (Mitchell *et al.*, 2001).

Recent studies have further expanded on job embeddedness, integrating it with other well-established organizational behaviour theories. For instance, Lee *et al.*, (2014) combined job embeddedness with the unfolding model of turnover, showing how embedded employees are less likely to quit when faced with negative job experiences. This highlights that job embeddedness not only explains why employees stay but also buffers the impact of adverse work events that might otherwise lead to resignation.

Additionally, researchers have explored how job embeddedness relates to the concept of "job crafting," where employees actively shape their roles to better align with their values and strengths (Tims *et al.*, 2013). Studies suggest that employees with high levels of job embeddedness are more likely to engage in job crafting, strengthening their bond with the organization and further reducing the chances of leaving (Rai and Maheshwari, 2021).

Global and Cultural Perspectives

Job embeddedness, though initially developed within Western organizational contexts, has proven to be a versatile concept, applicable across diverse industries and cultural settings. Different cultures place varying emphasis on the components of job embeddedness, and this variance significantly influences employee retention. For instance, in collectivist cultures like East Asia, the role of social connections or links—the relationships individuals form within and outside their organization—tends to hold greater importance. Ng and Feldman, (2013) found that in such cultures, the value placed on relationships and community ties strengthens job embeddedness, making it a critical factor in retaining employees.

In the context of the gig economy and remote work, job embeddedness has also evolved. With non-traditional work arrangements becoming more common, the way employees remain attached to their roles has shifted. Ruhle and Süß, (2020) explored this phenomenon, finding that while remote employees might experience fewer organizational links, they can still feel embedded through a strong personal connection to their role (fit) or the perceived sacrifices associated with leaving a stable job. As work environments become more flexible and decentralized, understanding how job embeddedness operates in these settings becomes crucial for organizations aiming to retain talent in an increasingly dynamic workforce.

Review of Literature on JE in Academia

Academicians, particularly in higher education institutions, face a unique set of challenges that influence their job satisfaction and commitment. Unlike many other sectors, job embeddedness among academicians is not solely driven by financial incentives but is deeply intertwined with factors such as academic freedom, research opportunities, collegial relationships, and work-life balance (Ramesh and Goyal, 2021). In the academic context, job embeddedness can be understood through the same three dimensions—links, fit, and sacrifice—as proposed by Mitchell *et al.*, (2001), though with added nuances given the specific nature of academic work.

Links

In academia, links represent the relationships that faculty members build within their institution, with colleagues, students, and administrative staff, as well as the broader academic community. These connections foster a sense of belonging and commitment, which is essential for faculty retention. Research by Kumar and Devi, (2019) highlights that in Indian higher education institutions (HEIs), faculty members who have strong mentorship

networks and opportunities for collaboration are more likely to feel embedded within their institutions. Furthermore, informal social networks, such as peer support groups, play a crucial role in fostering these connections, helping academicians feel integrated into their institution's academic community. In global studies, similar patterns have been observed. Hom *et al.*, (2012) noted that academic collaboration and collegial relationships are key to retaining faculty members in higher education institutions worldwide. The presence of supportive professional networks helps faculty members navigate the demands of academia, leading to greater job embeddedness.

Fit

The fit dimension of job embeddedness reflects how well faculty members perceive their values and goals align with those of their institution. In Indian HEIs, the fit between an academicians's personal ambitions—such as research output and career progression—and the institution's vision is critical. Academicians who perceive a strong fit are more likely to stay with their institutions because their goals are in harmony with the opportunities provided (Jena, 2021). However, with the rise of private universities and their diverse institutional cultures, achieving this sense of fit can be more complex. Mishra, (2020) observed that in private institutions, where performance metrics and industry collaborations are emphasized, there can be a mismatch between personal goals and institutional demands, reducing job embeddedness.

Globally, the concept of fit plays a similarly important role. For instance, Kraimer *et al.*, (2011) found that faculty members in Australian universities who felt their personal and professional values aligned with the institution's academic priorities reported higher levels of job embeddedness. This suggests that fit is a universal determinant of faculty retention, although specific factors influencing fit may vary depending on the region and institutional policies.

Sacrifice

The sacrifice dimension pertains to the perceived costs associated with leaving an institution. In academia, these sacrifices are not limited to financial considerations but also include the loss of professional networks, research opportunities, and access to resources. In India, the sacrifice of leaving a public university can be particularly high, as public institutions often provide job security and tenure—benefits highly valued by faculty members (Ramesh and

Goyal, 2021). The long-term financial benefits of tenure and government pensions create significant barriers to leaving, even when research funding or institutional support may be limited.

Private universities, in contrast, often offer competitive salaries but lack the long-term security associated with tenure. However, for faculty members with established research programs or strong professional reputations, leaving a position would still entail significant sacrifices, such as the disruption of ongoing research projects or the loss of academic standing. This trend is mirrored internationally. In the United States, for example, faculty members with tenure or strong research portfolios are less likely to leave their institutions, as the costs of leaving outweigh potential benefits (Nguyen *et al.*, 2020).

Gender and JE in Academia

The association among job embeddedness and gender among academicians has gained increasing attention, particularly in India, where cultural norms and expectations for men and women often differ. Female faculty members face unique challenges in balancing their academic careers with personal and familial responsibilities, which can influence their job embeddedness (Sharma and Jha, 2020). Studies suggest that female academicians are more likely to rely on the links dimension of job embeddedness to find support within their workplace, often through formal mentorships or collegial relationships. Kumari and Srivastava, (2018) found that female faculty members in public universities in India tend to have higher levels of JE when they have access to institutional support systems, such as flexible work hours and childcare facilities. These links create a sense of community and belonging that fosters retention. On the other hand, male faculty members tend to report higher job embeddedness globally due to their greater involvement in leadership roles and professional networks, which enhance their sense of fit with the institution's goals and culture (Allen, 2006).

Global Comparisons

While job embeddedness has been widely studied in Western contexts, research from developing nations like India provides valuable insights into how job embeddedness

functions in different cultural settings. In China, for example, Confucian values of loyalty to one's institution have been shown to contribute to higher levels of job embeddedness among university faculty (Ng and Feldman, 2013). Similarly, European studies by Coetzee and Schreuder, (2019) found that the sense of academic community and collegial relationships are central to job embeddedness in HEIs.

However, the factors influencing job embeddedness can vary significantly between developed and developing countries. In India, resource availability and institutional support play a more significant role in influencing job embeddedness compared to developed countries, where academic freedom and research opportunities are often prioritized (Ramesh and Goyal, 2021). This difference highlights the importance of context when studying job embeddedness, emphasizing that retention strategies must be tailored to the specific needs and conditions of the institution and its faculty.

Objectives of the Study

1. To explore the factors of the link to organization and JE
(For attaining this objective factors are confirmed in smart PLS4.0)
2. To associate the relationship between link to organization and JE.
(For achieving this objective Structural Equation Model (SEM) has been applied.)
3. To check the moderation effect of gender between link to organization and JE
(Categorical moderation with Multi group analysis (MGA) has been used.)

Hypothesis of the Study

To achieve the above said objective, following hypotheses are framed:

H₁: There is a significant relationship between link to organization and Job Embeddedness.

H₂: There is a significant difference of link to Organization in job Embeddedness among academicians on the basis of gender.

Research Methodology

This study uses an exploratory and descriptive research design focused on job embeddedness among academicians in India. Starting with an extensive literature review, the researchers developed measurement criteria for job embeddedness, with input from experts to ensure

accuracy. A structured questionnaire, originally designed by Mitchell et al. (2001), was adapted and distributed to gather data from academics across India, with a major focus on North Indian states (Punjab, Haryana, Uttar Pradesh, Jammu and Kashmir, and Rajasthan).

The sampling design included selecting sample units, areas, and sample size criteria. A total of 800 academics were approached, and 646 complete responses were obtained, achieving an 80.75% response rate. The sample size exceeded the recommended minimum of 380, aligning with Hair and Black's (2006) guidelines. A non-probability sampling technique, specifically convenience sampling, was employed due to its suitability for exploratory research. Data were collected using a five-point Likert scale questionnaire, with some items removed after exploratory factor analysis to improve reliability. The refined 33-item questionnaire was then used in the final analysis.

The demographic characteristics of the 646 respondents included in the analysis. Among the respondents, the age distribution is as follows: 28.64% are between 25-35 years, 39.78% are between 35-45 years, and 31.58% are over 45 years of age. In terms of gender, the sample comprises 52.48% male and 47.52% female respondents. Regarding marital status, 68.74% of respondents are married, while 31.26% are unmarried; of those married, 42.40% have a spouse working in the same city, while 27.10% have a spouse who is not working in the same city. These demographic details provide a comprehensive overview of the varied profiles of respondents within this study.

The study applies Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) using Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) to validate the job Embeddedness and link to organization construct. PLS-SEM, a versatile tool for complex models, is executed in two parts: the Measurement Model and the Structural Model, with this study focusing on the former. The Measurement Model assesses reliability and validity through reflective and formative constructs. In reflective constructs, indicators should load above 0.6, with internal consistency confirmed by Cronbach's alpha and Composite Reliability (both ≥ 0.7). Convergent validity, indicating shared variance, is met if Average Variance Extracted (AVE) exceeds 0.5. Discriminant validity, assessing construct uniqueness, is evaluated through Fornell-Larcker criteria. Additional checks include multicollinearity using the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF). The model's reliability and validity were achieved through these criteria, ensuring robust measurement for further structural analysis.

Results and Discussion

When examining the relationship between organizational support and job embeddedness, it's important to look at how different dimensions of support influence an employee's decision to stay with a company. In this study, Confirmatory factor Analysis has been applied to check the variables. Further Structural Equation Model has been applied, and then following this Categorical moderation with Multi group analysis (MGA) has been used. The results of the CFA are as below in figure 1.

Figure 1: Measurement Model of Link to Organization and Job Embeddedness

The diagram you provided represents of confirming the factors of Link to Organization and Job Embeddedness. Here's a breakdown of the elements and how they relate:

The "Link to Organization" is represented as independent variable on the left side. This is a latent construct, it is assessed through the observable indicators LO1 ("On the job, I interact frequently with my work group members"), LO2 ("I work closely with my co-workers"), LO3 ("I am a member of an effective work group"), LO4 ("I share a harmonious relation with my students"), LO5 ("I am active in one or more organization") respectively. On the right side, the blue circle represents the latent construct Job Embeddedness treated as dependent variable, assessed through the observable indicators JB1 to JB10. ("I have lot of

freedom on this job to decide how to pursue my goals.”, I like the authority and responsibility I have at this job”, “I feel like I am a good match for this job”, “My values are compatible with the organization’s value”, “The perks on this job are outstanding”, “I think people at work respect me a great deal”, “I would sacrifice a lot if I had to leave this job”, “My promotion opportunities are excellent here”, “I am well compensated for my level of performance” and lastly “The benefits are good on this job”) respectively. A details of all values are presented through Table.

Table1: Outer loadings of Link to Organization and Job Embeddedness

Variables	Items	Link to Organization	Job Embeddedness
Link to Organization	LO1	0.705	
	LO2	0.743	
	LO3	0.688	
	LO4	0.747	
	LO5	0.682	
Job Embeddedness	JB1		0.758
	JB2		0.728
	JB3		0.838
	JB4		0.783
	JB5		0.759
	JB6		0.700
	JB7		0.701
	JB8		0.741
	JB9		0.79
	JB10		0.748

Source: Primary Data

First condition is to confirm the factors is outer loadings. The numbers between the latent variable and these indicators (e.g., 0.705, 0.743, 0.688, 0.747 and 0.682) are factor loadings. These indicate how well each item (LO1 to LO5) reflects the underlying construct "Link to Organization." In this case, they range from 0.682 to 0.747, suggesting that all these items are greater than 0.6 as said by Garson, 2016 that factors loadings should be greater than 0.6. hence, first condition is fulfilled and all values contribute moderately well to the construct. The factor loadings between Job Embeddedness and its indicators range from 0.700 to 0.838. These values suggest a strong relationship between the indicators and the latent construct, meaning the items JB1 to JB10 are good representations of JE.

Reliability and Validity

Table 2: Reliability and Validity of Link to Organization and Job Embeddedness

Variables	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability (CR)	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Link to Organization	0.776	0.838	0.509
Job Embeddedness	0.816	0.830	0.571

Source: Primary Data

Above table provide a clear explanation of “Cronbach's Alpha”, “Composite Reliability” (CR), and “Average Variance Extracted” (AVE) for the variables Link to Organization and Job Embeddedness respectively. Cronbach’s Alpha is a measure of the internal consistency, which indicates how well the items in a construct are positively correlated with each other. A value of Link to Organization is 0.776 and Job Embeddedness is 0.816 shows good reliability. According to Hair et al. (2010), a Cronbach’s Alpha value between 0.7 and 0.9 is considered acceptable in most research settings. This means that the items related to "Link to Organization" and Job Embeddedness is consistently measuring the same underlying concept, ensuring reliability.

Composite Reliability is a more comprehensive measure of reliability than Cronbach’s Alpha, as it accounts for the differing loadings of the items. A CR value of Link to Organization" and Job Embeddedness 0.838 and 0.830 indicates strong reliability, exceeding the commonly accepted threshold of 0.7. Values above 0.7 suggest that the items are reliably measuring the Link to Organization and Job Embeddedness construct, offering a stronger internal consistency than Cronbach’s Alpha.

Average Variance Extracted (AVE) measures the amount of variance that a construct captures from its indicators relative to the amount of variance due to measurement error. An AVE of 0.509 and 0.571 means that the construct explains just over 50% of the variance in its indicators, indicating adequate convergent validity. Fornell and Larcker (1981) suggest that AVE should be greater than 0.5 to confirm that the construct explains a substantial portion of the variance in the indicators.

Discriminant validity

It is the extent to which a construct is truly distinct from other constructs, both conceptually and empirically. In other words, discriminant validity ensures that a given construct is not only unique but also different from other constructs in the model. It helps to verify that the items measuring one construct do not excessively overlap with items measuring another construct. There are most common methods for assessing discriminant validity is Fornell-Larcker Criterion.

Fornell-Larcker Criterion

Here is the Fornell-Larcker Criterion table based on the values provided for Job Embeddedness and Link to Organization:

Table 3: Fornell-Larcker Criterion

Variables	Job Embeddedness	Link to Organization
Job Embeddedness	0.756	-
Link to Organization	0.383	0.714

Source: Primary Data

According to the Fornell-Larcker Criterion, the square root of the AVE for each construct (diagonal values) should be greater than the correlations between that construct and any other construct (off-diagonal values). For Job Embeddedness (0.756), this value is greater than its correlation with Link to Organization (0.383), confirming discriminant validity. For Link to Organization (0.714), this value is also greater than the correlation with Job Embeddedness (0.383), again confirming discriminant validity. Hence, The Fornell-Larcker Criterion is satisfied in your model, confirming that the constructs Job Embeddedness and Link to Organization have discriminant validity—meaning they are distinct from one another in your measurement model. After satisfying the conditions, next is to check the structural Model between Link to Organization and Job Embeddedness.

Figure 2: Structural Model of Link to Organization and Job Embeddedness

A brief explanation of the Structural Model of Link to Organization and Job Embeddedness is presented through the table

Table 4: Structural Model output of Link to Organization to Job Embeddedness

Criteria for Link to Organization -> Job Embeddedness	Output
Original Sample (O) / Path Coefficient	0.383
Standard Deviation (STDEV)	0.030
R Square	0.147
f- Square	0.172
Q- Square	0.082
VIF (>1 < 5)	1.000
NFI (>0.9)	0.918
T Statistics (O/STDEV) (>1.96)	12.608
P Values	0.000
Hypothesis	H₁ (Accepted)

Source: Primary Data

The path coefficient represents the strength and direction of the relationship between the independent variable (Link to Organization) and the dependent variable (Job Embeddedness).

A coefficient of 0.383 indicates a moderately positive relationship because according to Garson's rule path coefficient should lie between -1 to +1. This means that as the "Link to Organization" increases, the level of "Job Embeddedness" tends to increase moderately. The standard deviation of the path coefficient shows the amount of variation in the path coefficient estimates across the samples used in the analysis. A low value of 0.030 suggests that there is minimal variability in this relationship across different samples, indicating that the estimate is stable.

The **R² value** measures the proportion of variance in the dependent variable (Job Embeddedness) that is explained by the independent variable (Link to Organization). An R² of 0.147 suggests that 14.7% of the variance in job embeddedness is explained by the link to the organization. Criteria is; less than 0.25 for low effect, >0.25 and less than 0.50 is medium and greater than 0.50 is large effect as said by Garson, 2016. This is a low moderate explanatory power, which is common in social sciences.

The **f-square** value assesses the effect size of the independent variable on the dependent variable. According to Cohen (1988), f^2 values can be interpreted as 0.02: Small effect, 0.15: Medium effect and 0.35: Large effect. An f^2 of 0.172 indicates a **medium effect**, meaning that "Link to Organization" has a moderate influence on "Job Embeddedness."

The **Q² value** measures the predictive relevance of the model for the endogenous construct (Job Embeddedness). A Q^2 value greater than 0 indicates that the model has predictive relevance for the construct. With a Q^2 of 0.082, this suggests that the model has medium predictive relevance for job embeddedness. **Variance Inflation Factor (VIF)** measures multicollinearity between the independent variables in the model. A VIF between 1 and 5 is acceptable and indicates that multicollinearity is not a concern. With a VIF of 1.000, there is no multicollinearity, ensuring the independent variable is not overly correlated with others. **Normed Fit Index (NFI)** assesses the goodness of fit of the model. NFI values above 0.9 are considered to show a good fit of the model to the data as said by Garson, 2016. An NFI of **0.918** indicates that the model fits the data well. The **T-statistic** indicates the **significance** of the path coefficient. A T-value greater than **1.96** implies significance at the 95% confidence level. With a **T-value of 12.704**, the path from "Link to Organization" to "Job Embeddedness" is highly significant. The **P-value** shows whether the path coefficient is statistically significant. A P-value less than **0.05** indicates significance. With a P-value of **0.000**, the relationship between "Link to Organization" and "Job Embeddedness" is statistically significant. Given the positive path coefficient, the T-value greater than 1.96, and a P-value of 0.000, the hypothesis that "**Link to Organization**" **positively influences** "**Job Embeddedness**" is accepted.

H₁: There is a significant relationship between link to organization and Job Embeddedness.

Moderation Effect

Moderation analysis can be of two types like continuous and categorical. In this study, categorical moderation has been applied for testing the results. Categorical Moderation effect means when the differences between two variables (dependent or independent) vary on a third (moderator) variable (Hair et al., 2013).

In this session, study has defined the objective that "*to study the moderation effect Gender in relation to Link to Organization and job Embeddedness among academicians*".

Academicians are taken on Gender basis i.e. Male and Female. For calculating the results following main hypothesis has been formulated:

H₍₂₎: There is a significant difference of link to Organization in job Embeddedness among academicians on the basis of gender

For attaining the sub-hypothesis moderation effect has been pertained. In this study, moderating effect is calculating among variables link to Organization and Job Embeddedness across Gender (Male (group1) and Female (group2)). For this purpose Partial Least Square Multigroup Analysis (PLS-MGA) has been applied. It is a non-parametric technique to assess the significant group difference which is based on the PLS-SEM bootstrapping technique. According to this approach, the difference between path coefficients of group-specific will be defined as significant at a 5 per cent significance level when the p-value is lesser than 0.05. (Sarstedt et al., 2011)

Moderating Effect between Link to Organization and Job Embeddedness

For examining the moderating effect of Gender (Male (group1=339 cases) and Female (group2=307 cases)) in the relationship between Link to Organization (independent) and Job Embeddedness(dependent) the following hypothesis has been developed.

Figure3: Moderating Effect between Link to Organization and Job Embeddedness

Table 5: Multi-Group Analysis of Link to Organization and Job Embeddedness

Relationship	Gender	Criteria	Values	Results	Hypothesis
Link to Organization - ^ Job Embeddedness	Male (399)	p ⁽¹⁾	0.95	Significant	(H ₂)Accepted
		se(p ⁽¹⁾)	0.027		
		T-value	35.249		
		P-value	0.000		
	Female (307)	p ⁽²⁾	0.823	Significant	
		se(p ⁽²⁾)	0.015		
		T-value	56.041		
		P-value	0.000		
	Male/female	p ^{(1)* p⁽²⁾}	0.141	Significant	
		T-value	4.373		
		P-value	0.000		

Source: PLS-SEM output

Note: P⁽¹⁾ and P⁽²⁾ are path coefficient of male and female; se(p⁽¹⁾) and se(p⁽²⁾) are standard error of male and feamble; p<.05

Table 5. defines the output of Multigroup analysis and testing the hypothesis on the basis of gender; Male is consider as group 1 with 339 cases and Female as group 2 with 307 cases have significance difference between link to organization and job Embeddedness.

Report→ Bootstrapping→ path coefficients (Mean, STDEV, T-Values) →standard errors”. As table displays the values of path coefficient (P¹ and P²) for Male (moderating variable) is 0.950 and Female (moderating variable) is 0.823 in association between independent (link to organization) and dependent variable (job Embeddedness). Standard error (se(p¹ = 0.027)) of the male in Group 1, run bootstrap with 339 cases; the standard error (se(p²=0.015)) of the female in Group 2, run bootstrap with also 307 cases. There are no issue of standard error. T-value should be greater than 1.96 as said by Garson, 2016. The respective T-values for Male is 35.249 and 56.041 for female. It indicates that both group male and female reached the criteria of significance level of T-statistics. P-values for both groups male and female also find significant at 5 percent of level. It is good for current study. Results

indicated that, value of path coefficient ($0.950 > 0.823$) has been found greater for the male in comparison to the female in relationship between link to organization and job Embeddedness. The values of significant difference (0.001) between the path coefficients of male v/s female are found at 5 per cent significance level and t =-value (4.373) is greater than 1.96 (Garson, 2016) which means that gender (male v/s female) have a significant difference. So based on significance difference (t-value > 1.96 and P-value < 0.05 percent), it is concluded that moderating effect of male and Female on the basis of gender is found significant. Further result reveals that relationship between link to organization and job Embeddedness is higher in case of male as compare to female. Thus, hypothesis stands accepted.

H₍₂₎: There is a significant difference in link to organization among academicians on the basis of gender.

Findings of the Study

The analysis reveals that Link to Organization significantly influences Job Embeddedness among academicians. The path coefficient of 0.383 indicates a moderately positive relationship, suggesting that as the link to the organization increases, job embeddedness tends to increase. This is further supported by the high T-value of 12.704 and a statistically significant P-value of 0.000, confirming that the hypothesis (H1) regarding the positive relationship between Link to Organization and Job Embeddedness is accepted. Additionally, the analysis indicates a significant moderating effect of gender on this relationship. Male academicians show a stronger link to job embeddedness (path coefficient of 0.950) compared to female academicians (0.823), suggesting that gender plays a crucial role in the perception of organizational links and job embeddedness.

Limitations

Several limitations should be noted in this study. Firstly, the sample is restricted to a specific geographic region, which may limit the generalizability of the findings to other contexts or countries. Secondly, the cross-sectional design of the study do not allow for the examination of causal relationships over time. Additionally, the reliance on self-reported measures could introduce biases, as faculty members may respond in socially desirable ways. Lastly, while this study focuses on gender as a moderating variable, other demographic factors such as

age, academic rank, or field of study could also influence job embeddedness but were not examined.

Future Directions and Conclusions

Future research should consider a more diverse sample across various geographic regions and institutional types to enhance the generalizability of the findings. Longitudinal studies could be beneficial in understanding how job embeddedness evolves over time in relation to organizational links. Additionally, exploring other moderating variables such as age, academic rank, and work experience could provide a more nuanced understanding of the factors affecting job embeddedness. Finally, qualitative approaches could be utilized to gain deeper insights into the lived experiences of faculty members regarding their links to organizations and their overall job satisfaction.

The findings underscore the importance of fostering strong organizational links within academic institutions to enhance job embeddedness. The results indicate that positive relationships with colleagues, students, and administrative staff are vital for retention and commitment among faculty members. Moreover, the study highlights that gender differences exist in the strength of the relationship between organizational links and job embeddedness, suggesting that tailored strategies may be required to engage male and female faculty effectively.

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